

D2.1

Identification of the most representative biobased value chains

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ABBREVIATIONS

AHP	Analytic Hierarchy process
CE	Environmental criteria
CS	Socioeconomic criteria
CT	Technical criteria
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation
FSC	Forest Stewardship Council
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
ISCC	ISCC Plus of the International Sustainability and Carbon Certification
N.P.R.S.	Not put up for retail sale
PRODCOM	is an annual survey for the collection and dissemination of statistics on the production of industrial (mainly manufactured) goods, both in value and quantity terms, in the EU.
QGIS	Quantum Geographical Information System
RSB	RSB Advanced Products of Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials
RSPO	Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil
VC	Value Chain

Executive Summary

This deliverable has been prepared under Task 2.1 “Identifying most representative biobased value chains” in the Work package WP2 – Quantification of global trade flows of biobased value chains. The objective of WP2 is mapping and evaluating the most representative biobased value chains, collecting data on global trade flows for (un)certified biobased value chains and giving insight in relation between certification and the trade in the European Union (EU).

The goal of Task 2.1 is to identify and rank the biobased value chains in the EU in terms of their potential to contribute to sustainable development. By using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and identifying the criteria and sub-criteria for the rankings, the study aimed to provide insights into which value chains may have the greatest potential for sustainable development in the EU.

In this work, six industrial sectors were considered which are textile, woodworking, plastic, pulp and paper, construction and chemical, and three biobased value chains were selected per sector. This was done according to considerations such as: specific value chain (from and specific resource to a specific product), existence of sustainability certification schemes, amount of production in Europe, etc (described in chapter 2).

Once the biobased value chains were selected (described in chapter 3), this study used the AHP to rank the biobased value chains. For this, criteria (environmental, socioeconomic, technical) and subcriteria (potential biobased share of the final product, estimated percentage share of biobased products in total marketed, presence of environmental concerns, relevance to EU policy priorities, market size, market growth, presence of social concerns, innovative character of the value chain, feedstock availability in the EU, biobased final product produced in the EU and valorisation of residues and wastes) were defined in order to cover the main considerations to produce sustainable products.

The relative importance of each of these criteria and subcriteria has been scored by collecting input from 9 experts (from members of the Advisory Board and experts from the three sister projects). For each of the subcriteria, a scale from 1 to 9 has been drawn up with a description of what each value means, and through desk research a score has been given to each value chain for each subcriteria.

The AHP method has been applied to all the data collected and the final ranking of the chains has been obtained. The 3 biobased value chains that scored the highest are:

- Mulch film from organic waste, which belong to the plastic sector and the agricultural subsector.
- Prefabricated buildings from wood and wheat straw, which belong to the construction sector and the building envelop subsector.
- Adhesives from tall oil, which belong to the chemical sector and the adhesives subsector.

In addition, it has also been found that the biobased value chain itself (the raw material and specific product taken into account) is more relevant to obtain the final score in the final ranking than the sector to which it belongs, as the score is mainly dictated by the specific raw material and product selected rather than the sector.

The information carried in this task will be used as input in the Task 2.2 for collection of trade flows on the most representation biobased value chains and for Task 4.2 which concerns identification of three biobased value chains for cost benefit analysis.

1. Introduction

This deliverable has been prepared under Task 2.1 “Identifying most representative biobased value chains” in the Work package WP2 – Quantification of global trade flows of biobased value chains.

Bioeconomy can be defined as an economy where the basic components of materials are derived from renewable biological resources. Thus, it is closely related to the agricultural and forestry sectors and the residues and wastes generated from these sectors. Essentially, biobased economy involves a transition to using biobased alternatives to the conventional fossil based products providing environmental benefits and creating socio-technical transformations in the society.

This report presents the results of a study that focused on the selection and ranking of value chains in six sectors: pulp and paper, construction, chemistry, plastic, textile, and woodworking, with the goal of identifying representative biobased value chains in the EU. In order to do so the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) has been used, where criteria and subcriteria were defined and ranking was carried out providing the evaluation of the biobased value chains considered as well as comparison between them to define which value chains may have the greatest potential for sustainable development in the EU.

The deliverable is structured as follows:

In **Chapter 2** the **methodology** followed to carry out this work is explained in two sections: the first one focused on how the biobased value chains were selected, and the second one describing how the ranking was done using a mathematical model (Analytic Hierarchy Process).

Chapter 3 provides the **selected biobased value chains** together with a short description of them.

Chapter 4 describes the main **results** obtained divided in three section: (i) result of the weight of each criteria and subcriteria taking into account, (ii) results of the score associated to each subcriteria in each value chain, and (iii) final ranking of the selected value chains.

Finally, **Chapter 5** gives the **conclusions** of the work carried out and the link with the other task of the project in which the information obtained in this report will be used and extended.

2. Methodology

This chapter introduces the methodology followed for the selection of the value chains, and the mathematical model used to rank the biobased value chains selected.

2.1 Methodology followed for the selection of the value chains.

Biobased value chain can be defined as a series of activities that use biological resources to produce a biobased product. In D1.1 classification of biological resources that can be used in these value chains were made: primary dedicated, primary residues, secondary residues, and tertiary residues and wastes. Moreover, biobased products were categorized under six sectors which are industrial sectors considered to be of interest for the European biobased economy and which are prominent sectors identified in the European Commission's Bioeconomy Strategy. These are:

- **Chemicals sector:** the most important industrial sector in Europe, corresponding to 17% of EU manufacture production. In 2021 its market value reached 594,000 million of euros [1].
- **Construction sector:** this sector represents the 9% of the EU's Gross Domestic product (GDP) with a production value in 2020 of 1.6 billion of euros [2].
- **Textile sector:** this sector represents the 1.5% of the EU GDP with a market value of 59,000 million of euros [3].
- **Plastics sector:** in Europe this sector represents a market value of 102,000 million of euros [4].
- **Pulp and paper sector:** the European pulp and paper sector reached a production of 91 million of tons of paper in 2019, with a market value of 83,000 million of euros [5].
- **Woodworking sector:** the European woodworking sector reached a turnover during 2019 of 177 billion of euros.

Since these industrial sectors are very broad and generate a wide variety of final products, 3 value chains per sector were selected based on the following criteria:

- The selection of the value chain must be **specific**, i.e., from a specific biological resource to a specific biobased product.
- Existence of sustainability **certification schemes** and labels relevant in the biobased chain based on a coverage of different types of feedstocks and sectors. The certification schemes for biobased supply chains are focused on three aspects:
 - Feedstock certification: it evaluates the sustainability of the raw material. Some specific feedstock certificates that may be considered are Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) for wood or Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO) for oil palm.
 - Biobased product certification: it evaluates the sustainability of the biobased product chain. Some specific certificates that may be considered are ISCC Plus of the International Sustainability and Carbon Certification (ISCC) [6] and RSB Advanced Products of Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials (RSB).
 - Ecolabel: these labels are given to environmentally sustainable products. They are specific for sector/product group (e.g., cleaning products, paper). Besides the EU Ecolabel applicable at EU, there is for example Blue Angel in Germany or Nordic Swan in Nordic countries.

- **Specific biological resource:** The 4 main biological resource categories identified in Task 1.1. have been considered to build the biobased value chains, ensuring that the four categories are reflected. These categories are described in Table 1:

Table 1. Biological resources classification from Task 1.1

CATEGORIES IDENTIFIED	DESCRIPTION
Primary dedicated	Biomass which has been purposely grown as such or which constitutes the primary result of production.
Primary residues	Biomass that is generated as an element of production and/or management but is not the main product. The primary residues are parts of biomass that are left on the field or in the forest after harvesting of the biomass.
Secondary residues	The secondary residues are all forms of biomass that arise from processing of the biomass in industry. Such residues typically are available in larger quantities at processing facilities, such as the agro-food industry, saw- and paper mills, and the like.
Tertiary residues and wastes	The tertiary residues or wastes are those sources that have already had a use (post-consumer) and that consist partly or fully of biological material such as organic fraction of municipal solid waste (MSW), waste and demolition wood, sludges, and so on.

- **Amount of production in the EU:** the selection of the value chain was done not only according to the biobased potential of the final product (understood as the ability of being biobased) but also to its presence in the current market, assuming a greater economic impact. This is mainly done through the value provided by PRODCOM [7]. PRODCOM is managed by Eurostat, the statistical office of the European Union, which collects and classifies all the manufactured products in the EU according to a specific number with eight figures. Using this PRODCOM data and analysing the market data and statistics, the three highest market size final products were selected from each sector. In other words, to conduct a more heterogeneous and comprehensive sector analysis by only considering one final product per subsector (PRODCOM groups and market statistics [2], [5], [8], [9], [10], [11]), other final products with greater market presence might have been overlooked.

The obtained data, together with results from the specific literature research of the sectors and feedback from the partners of the consortium, were used to define the definitive value chains.

As depicted in Figure 1, three subsectors have been chosen for each of the six sectors. For the "Pulp and paper" sector, the selection was based on the data of Paper and Board Consumption for each application published by Cepi [5], from which the three main subsectors were identified as: "Packaging Paper and Board" (NACE Code: 17.21), "Graphic Papers" (NACE Code: 17.23), and "Sanitary." (NACE Code: 17.22). These subsectors were responsible for producing, respectively, 53, 25, and over 7 million tons of products in 2021 [5].

Regarding the Construction sector, the selection of subsectors were made based on information available in the ECSO report "Fostering the international competitiveness of EU construction

enterprises" [2]. This report outlines the sectoral activities in the construction sector and utilizes the values of sold production of all final products encompassed under NACE code 16.23 from Eurostat. The main subsectors of the sector were accordingly identified as follows: the "Building envelope" (NACE Code: 16.23.20), wooden structures (16.23.11.50) and the manufacturing of interior elements (NACE Code: 16.23.11.00). These subsectors reached the following production values in 2022, respectively: 10, 8 and 7 million € [2; 7].

Regarding the Chemistry sector, the identification of the main subsectors was conducted using data from the "Roadmap for the Chemical Industry in Europe towards a Bioeconomy" [8]. It was observed that "Lubricants" (NACE Code: 20.59.41), "Solvents", and "Adhesives" (NACE Code: 20.52) are the subsectors that, after excluding those belonging to other sectors, exhibit the highest production volumes (fossil & bio-based chemicals). They generate the following values: 3900 kt/year Lubricants, 5000 kt/year Solvents, and 8580 kt/year Adhesives [8].

For the Plastics sector, the subsectors of "Consumer goods", "Agriculture," and "Packaging" were selected as the most relevant, as they represent, according to European Bioplastics, the largest global production capacities of bioplastics. They respectively accounted for 13%, 5%, and 43% of the production in 2023 [9].

For identification of the subsectors in the textile sector, in addition to consulting the "European Report on Advanced Technologies for the Textile Industry" on the main types of final products in which the EU sector is specialized [10], the values of sold production of all final textile products were considered primarily within the PRODCOM listing between codes NACE 13.92 and 14.19. Based on this, the main subsectors selected were "Clothing" (NACE Code: 14.12 – 14.19; 14.31 and 14.39), "Furniture" (NACE Code: 13.92 – 13.93), and "Industry" (13.94; 13.96), as these were identified as the main areas into which the sector was segregated according to the applications in the sector [7; 10].

Finally, from the Woodworking sector, based on the distribution between the different segments that make up the woodworking industry as indicated in the European Forest based sector report "Vision 2040" [11], "Furniture," representing 41% of the market and encompassing NACE code 31, was selected. Wood manufacturing excluding furniture (NACE Code: 16) accounts for 47% of the sector. From this, the two subgroups "Carpentry pieces" (16.24) and "Manufactured articles" (16.29) were selected based on the sales values of production published by Eurostat [7; 11].

As a result, Figure 1 summarises the 18 subsectors considered.

Figure 1. Main subsectors identified for each sector.

2.2 Methodology followed to rank the selected value chains.

2.2.1 Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)

The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is a multicriteria decision making methodology created by the mathematician Thomas L. Saaty in the 70s with the objective to transfer human perceptions into numerical values [12]. It is a commonly used method for the selection of a discrete set of alternatives in a context where multiple scenarios, actors and criteria are involved. It involves the following three stages:

- (i) Modelling the problem: The mission, relevant criteria, sub-criteria for each criteria, actors and alternatives are structured by using a hierarchy.
- (ii) Valuation: The preferences of the experts are incorporated by means of pairwise comparison matrices between the elements of the hierarchy evaluating the criteria and sub-criteria by comparing them pairwise, using a scale of importance (Saaty's scale Table 2). The Saaty's fundamental scale is used for the elicitation of judgments.
- (iii) Prioritisation and synthesis: The results then are synthesized using a mathematical formula to produce a ranking of the alternatives being considered. The global priorities are derived by the application of the hierarchical composition principle.

Table 2. Saaty’s scale [9].

Saaty’s Scale		
Intensity of importance	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal importance	Two elements contribute equally to the objective
2	Between equal and moderate importance	
3	Moderate importance	Experience and judgements slightly favour one element over another
4	Between moderate and strong importance	
5	Strong importance	Experience and judgement strongly favour one element over another
6	Between strong and very strong importance	
7	Very strong importance	One element is favoured very strongly over another, its dominance is demonstrated in practice
8	Between very strong and extreme importance	
9	Extreme importance	The evidence favouring one element over another is of the highest possible order of affirmation

This mathematical model has been chosen in this study in order to rank the most representative biobased value chains selected. Following this method:

- Different criteria and sub-criteria were selected (described in detail in section 2.2.2)
- The valuation of these criteria and subcriteria were done through the involvement of experts in this field (members of the Advisory Board and technical experts of the three sister projects SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, HARMONITOR and STAR4BIOBASED) and desk research. The experts assessed the weight of each criteria and subcriteria, and through the desk research specific information was sought for each biobased value chain and subcriteria. In both cases the Saaty’s scale was considered to achieve this goal. Results from these subcriteria were represented with QGIS (CT-2, CS-3).
- The prioritisation of the biobased value chains was done taking into account the previous information using the software XLSTAT, in which the multicriteria process can be easily incorporated.

Figure 2 shows schematically the summary of the AHP methodology followed where CT, CS, and CE refer to technical, socioeconomic and environmental criteria respectively and VC refer to the biobased value chain.

Figure 2. Methodology followed in the task 2.1 to evaluate the value chains.

2.2.2 Criteria and subcriteria selected

The United Nations (UN) recognizes the importance of environmental, socioeconomic, and technical criteria to promote sustainable development [13]. By considering all three criteria, balanced decisions can be taken to assure the sustainability of the biobased industry and its economic viability, environmental production and social equity. Accordingly, the biobased value chains are evaluated by subcriteria, which are more specific actions derived from these three main criteria.

ENVIRONMENTAL CRITERIA (CE)

Environmental evaluation ensures that the nature is protected and preserved for future generations. By considering how a project affects the environment, negative impacts can be identified and more friendly practices can be promoted. In order to determinate the impact of each value chain, four environmental aspects are evaluated using a scale from 1 to 9. The environmental aspects evaluated are the following:

- CE1: Potential biobased share of the final product

Biobased share refers to the percentage of renewable or biobased sources, which the biobased product is made of. The main part of this data has been taken from the European Report of Biobased Market, which depicts 15 successful European biobased products [14]. However, some final products haven't been described in this document, specially from the pulp and paper, woodworking, and construction sectors, therefore their potential (CE1) and actual (CE2) biobased percentages have been obtained from products sold in the EU and certified according to European sustainability policies, since these certificates mention the minimum threshold for bio-based contents of the final product in the value chain could be considered reliable. Table 3 indicates the description of the meaning of all potential bio-based shares (from 1 to 9) according the Saaty's scale for this subcriteria.

Table 3. Saaty's scale followed for the potential Biobased share of the final product subcriteria.

Potential Biobased share of the final product			
CE	Environmental	CE-1	Description
		1	<5%
		2	5-10%
		3	10-20%
		4	20-30%
		5	30-40%
		6	40-50%
		7	50-70%
		8	70-90%
		9	90-100%

- CE2: Estimated percentage share of biobased products in total marketed.

The estimated percentage share of biobased products in total marketed describes their actual replaced conventional fossil-based inputs by bio-based inputs counterparts. The value of this subcriteria is higher if the product offers full replacement of a fossil-based product in the market. The value is low if the conventional product in the market is already biobased e.g., paper. For this purpose, data available from a number of market research reports have been used (references are indicated in section 4.2.2). Table 4 indicates the description of the meaning of all the values (from 1 to 9) according the Saaty's scale for this subcriteria.

Table 4. Saaty's scale followed for the estimated percentage share of biobased products in total marketed subcriteria.

Estimated percentage share of biobased products in total marketed			
CE	Environmental	CE-2	Description
		1	90-100%
		2	70-90%
		3	50-70%

Estimated percentage share of biobased products in total marketed			
		4	40-50%
		5	30-40%
		6	20-30%
		7	10-20%
		8	5-10%
		9	<5%

- CE3: Presence of environmental concerns

Different biobased value chains can have different degree of environmental impact e.g., energy demand, impact on water, air and soil quality.

The evaluation of this criteria has been done using two factors. Firstly, considering to which sector the value chain belongs to and its grade of environmental concern. According to the literature (indicated in section 4.2 for each sector), the environmental impact in decreasing order would be as follow: chemical sector, plastic sector, pulp and paper sector, construction sector, textile sector and woodworking. Secondly, considering the feedstock used in the value chain. The impact is lower if secondary and tertiary residues are used in the biobased value chains compared to primary dedicated and residues. Table 5 indicates the description of the meaning of all the values (from 1 to 9) according the Saaty's scale for this subcriteria.

Table 5. Saaty's scale followed for the assessment of Presence of environmental concerns subcriteria.

Presence of environmental concerns			
		CE-3	Description
CE	Environmental	1	Extreme concern: Primary dedicated with high negative impact on the environment and biodiversity preservation due to the pollutants and the value chain process
		2	Very high concern: Primary dedicated with negative impact on the environment and biodiversity preservation due to the pollutants and the value chain process
		3	High concern: Primary dedicated and generation of low levels of pollutants, without affecting directly biodiversity, but concern of food competition
		4	Medium-high concern: Primary dedicated with low negative impact on the environment, producing low pollutants, but also valuable products
		5	Medium concern: Primary residues with adverse impact on the environment caused from their use in the biobased industry (e.g., soil quality)
		6	Medium-low concern: Primary residues with generation of low levels of pollutants, without adverse effect on biodiversity

Presence of environmental concerns			
		7	Low concern: Primary residues with low negative impact on the environment, no adverse effect from their use in the biobased industry
		8	Very low concern: Secondary residues + tertiary residues with very low negative impact on the environment, producing low pollutants, but also valuable products
		9	No concern: Secondary residues + tertiary residues and with no negative impact on the environment, producing low pollutants, but also valuable products

- CE4: Relevance to EU policy priorities

In this subcriteria a distinction was made between value chains in terms of their relevance to "EU policy priorities" as expressed in overarching frameworks and strategies e.g., EU Green Deal, Taxonomy regulation, Sustainable carbon cycles, EU Bioeconomy Strategy, Circular Economy Action Plan. Value chains for which no specific or concrete support was provided by EU policy, were assigned a moderately positive score. For value chains, where a concrete promotion by EU policy was seen, were assigned a very positive score, conversely for value chains where a concrete contradiction with the recent EU policy priorities was seen were assigned a very negative score. Table 6 indicates the description of the meaning of all the values (from 1 to 9) according the Saaty’s scale for this subcriteria.

Table 6. Saaty’s scale followed for the assessment of Relevance to EU policy priorities subcriteria.

Relevance to EU policy priorities			
CE	Environmental	CE-4	Description
		1	This value chain is in contradiction with the recent EU policy priorities
		2	This value chain somewhat contradicts with the recent EU policy priorities
		3	This value chain is slightly contradiction with the recent EU policy priorities
		4	This value chain neither supported nor contradicted with the EU policy priorities
		5	This value chain includes some aspect of the EU policy priorities
		6	This value chain is slightly supported by EU policy priorities
		7	This value chain is relevant with regard to EU policy priorities
		8	This value chain is very relevant with regard to policy priorities
		9	This value chain is at the focus point of recent EU policy priorities

SOCIOECONOMIC CRITERIA (CS)

Socioeconomic evaluation ensures that a project or policy benefits society, rather than just a select few groups. By considering how a project or policy will affect different groups of people, decision-makers can identify and address potential social and economic inequalities and promote greater equity and inclusion. In order to determinate the impact of each value chain, three socioeconomic aspects are evaluated using a number scale from 1 to 9. The aspects evaluated are the next ones:

- CS1: Market size

The market size is a parameter that describes the economic value of all transactions in the market for a period of a full year (references are indicated in section 4.2.2). In this way, the current socioeconomic impact of the final product can be evaluated. Table 7 indicates the description of the meaning of all the values (from 1 to 9) according the Saaty’s scale for this subcriteria.

Table 7. Saaty’s scale followed for the assessment of Market size subcriteria.

Market size			
CS	Socioeconomic	CS-1	Description
		1	<10 billion USD
		2	10-60 billion
		3	60-100 billion
		4	100-150 billion
		5	150-200 billion
		6	200-250 billion
		7	250-300 billion
		8	300-350 billion
		9	more than 350 billion

- CS2: Market growth

The market growth is a parameter evaluated through the compound annual growth rate, that expresses the value market growth expected with respect to the previous years. This parameter allows to know the economic impact in the coming years, and the degree of priority of the biobased value chain (references are indicated in section 4.2.2). Table 8 indicates the description of the meaning of all the values (from 1 to 9) according the Saaty’s scale for this subcriteria.

Table 8. Saaty’s scale followed for the assessment of Market growth subcriteria.

Market growth			
CS	Socioeconomic	CS-2	Description
		1	<1%
		2	1-2%
		3	2-3%
		4	3-4%
		5	4-5%
		6	5-6%
		7	6-7%
		8	7-8%
		9	>8%

- CS3: Presence of social concerns

This sub-criterion indicates social problems (e.g. child labour, gender inequality) related to the raw material and its value chain. For this purpose, the origin of the biological resource used in the value chain is determined using the corresponding production and import values extracted from the database of the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) [15]. Based on this information, a social value attribution exercise is carried out for the regions involved (the EU itself and the three main global exporters of the raw material) using the "Social Progress Index" [16], which measures the social performance of the countries. The index is structured around 12 components drawn from three broad groups, which are as follows:

- Basic Human Needs
 - o Nutrition & Basic Medical Care
 - o Water & Sanitation
 - o Shelter
 - o Personal Safety
- Foundations of wellbeing
 - o Access to Basic Knowledge
 - o Access to Information & Communications
 - o Health & Wellness
 - o Environmental Quality
- Opportunity
 - o Personal Rights
 - o Personal Freedom & Choice
 - o Inclusiveness
 - o Access to Advanced Education

Each of the twelve components of the framework, as can be seen in the next figure, comprises between four and six specific performance indicators [17].

Based on the data collected by the creators of this index for each of these indicators, a score has been established in accordance with the social performance of each country, i.e. the higher the value, the better the situation of the corresponding country.

As a result, the sub-criterion exposes the presence of social concerns linked to the product as a consequence of the raw material used, taking into account both its origin and the quantity that is produced in and outside the EU.

Table 9 indicates the description of the meaning of all the values (from 1 to 9) according the Saaty's scale for this subcriteria.

Table 9. Saaty's scale followed for the assessment of Presence of social concerns subcriteria.

Presence of social concerns			
CS	Socioeconomic	CS-3	Description
		1	0-20
		2	20-30
		3	30-40
		4	40-50
		5	50-60
		6	60-70
		7	70-80
		8	80-90
		9	90-100

TECHNICAL CRITERIA (CT)

Technical evaluation ensures that a project or policy is feasible, effective, and efficient. By considering the practical and functional aspects of a project or policy, decision-makers can identify and address potential logistical or operational challenges and ensure that resources are used effectively and efficiently. In order to determine the impact of each value chain, four technical aspects are evaluated using a number scale from 1 to 9. The aspects evaluated are listed below:

- CT1: Innovative character of the value chain

The technological innovation of the value chain is evaluated using two criteria, simultaneously, obtained from reviews for each sector.

- The innovation in the feedstock. The valorisation of residues as an alternative raw material in the value chain is considered an innovation in the production process.
- The level of maturity of the technology. The technologies with lower maturity level are considered more innovative than very implemented technologies. This point is can be evaluated also, through the year when the technology was implemented.

Table 10 indicates the description of the meaning of all the values (from 1 to 9) according the Saaty's scale for this subcriteria.

Table 10. Saaty's scale followed for the assessment of Presence of social concerns subcriteria.

Presence of social concerns			
CT	Technical	CT-1	Description
		1	No innovation in the production process of the final and intermediate products as well as in the selection of the raw material
		2	No innovation in the production process of the final and intermediate products and low innovation in the selection of the raw material
		3	Low innovation in the production process of the final and intermediate products and low innovation in the selection of the raw material
		4	Low innovation in the production process of the final and intermediate products and medium innovation in the selection of the raw material
		5	Medium innovation in the production process of the final and intermediate products and medium innovation in the selection of the raw material
		6	Medium innovation in the production process of the final and intermediate products and high innovation in the selection of the raw material
		7	High innovation in the production process of the final and intermediate products and high innovation in the selection of the raw material
		8	High innovation in the production process of the final and intermediate products and very high innovation in the selection of the raw material
		9	Very high innovation in the production process of the final and intermediate products and very high innovation in the selection of the raw material

- CT2: Feedstock availability in the EU

The criterion "Feedstock availability in the EU" is intended to indicate the ease/difficulty of obtaining sufficient raw material in the EU area. For this purpose, the production and import quantities of raw material in the EU, previously obtained for subcriteria CS3, are used, considering that the import percentage corresponds to the percentage of raw material not available within the EU, i.e. the higher

the import, the more difficult it will be to obtain sufficient raw material. Table 11 indicates the description of the meaning of all the values (from 1 to 9) according the Saaty's scale for this subcriteria.

Table 11. Saaty's scale followed for the assessment of Feedstock availability in the EU subcriteria.

Feedstock availability in the EU			
CT	Technical	CT-2	Description
		1	100 % imported
		2	85-99 % imported
		3	70-85 % imported
		4	60-70 % imported
		5	50-60 % imported
		6	40-50 % imported
		7	30-40 % imported
		8	15-30% imported
		9	0-15 % imported

- CT3: Biobased final product produced in the EU

This subcriteria evaluates the technical capacity of EU to produce the selected biobased products, taking into consideration production and import quantities. Most of said data could be obtained from the PRODCOM platform. In the few cases where volumetric data was not available in PRODCOM, economic data was sourced. Finally, for products not registered in PRODCOM, other information sources were used, such as EU technical reports. A simple calculation was defined for the ranking, where higher values correspond to a higher European capacity of covering the production of a respective item (rather than depending on imports):

$$CT3 = \frac{\text{Total Production EU}}{(\text{Total Production EU} + \text{Total Imports EU})} \cdot 100$$

Importantly, while being a straightforward evaluation for 100% biobased value chains (such as wood-based products in construction, and woodworking sectors), the demand of most novel biobased products is much higher than its current production. These are currently hampered by supply chain complexity and low feedstock availability (particularly problematic for feedstocks that compete with food and/or very large market sizes), and technological immaturity of conversion processes to replace fossil-based value chains. Therefore, the CT-3 value gives an indication of the EU capacity for producing the selected final products, but this does not mean that said production is 100% biobased at the moment. Nonetheless, by coupling it with the results from other technical, environmental, and social subcriteria, a precise overview of each value chain can be obtained. Table 12 indicates the description of the meaning of all the values (from 1 to 9) according the Saaty's scale for this subcriteria.

Table 12. Saaty's scale followed for the assessment of production potential of Biobased final product in the EU subcriteria.

Biobased final product produced in the EU			
CT	Technical	CT-3	Description
		1	0%-15%
		2	15%-30%
		3	30%-40%
		4	40%-50%
		5	50%-60%
		6	60%-70%
		7	70%-85%
		8	85%-99%
		9	100%

- CT4: Valorisation of residues and wastes

This technical criteria is mainly related with the feedstock used, in which the evaluation is done taking into account on which category of the Table 1 the biological resource belongs to. As an example, using tertiary residues is the most preferred score and the use of primary dedicated the least preferred score. Table 13 indicates the description of the meaning of all the values (from 1 to 9) according the Saaty's scale for this subcriteria.

Table 13. Saaty's scale followed for the assessment of Valorisation of residues and wastes subcriteria.

Valorisation of residues and wastes			
CT	Technical	CT-4	Description
		1	Primary dedicated resources, no valorization of residues
		2	Primary dedicated resources, with also valorization of residues in chain (i.e. process residues for feed/energy)
		3	Primary dedicated resources, with also valorization of residues in chain (i.e. by-products produced on-site from its process residues)
		4	Primary dedicated resources with co-feed of primary residues (i.e., wheat and wheat straw valorization on the same site)
		5	Primary residues for low value application
		6	Primary residues for high value application
		7	Secondary residues for low value application
		8	Secondary residues for high value application
		9	Tertiary residues

3. Value chains selected

In this chapter, the value chains selected from the sectors are presented, considered to be of interest for the defossilization of the European economy as identified in the European Commission's Bioeconomy Strategy [18].

3.1 Pulp and paper sector

Based on the methodology outlined in section 2.1, for the pulp and paper sector three value chains were selected, one per main subsectors identified. These main subsectors in the pulp and paper sector were identified through the Cepi's key statistics 2021 [5], which are illustrated in Figure 3:

Figure 3. Subsectors identified in pulp and paper sector.

The following final products from the Pulp and Paper sector were selected based on the methodology described in section 2.1: Napkins, Graphic paper and Carton and boxes. Each one of these products are described below.

- **Sanitary paper (napkins) [19]**

As sanitary paper, napkins are the most produced and sold product in Europe. Based on specific literature, napkins are made by cellulose obtained from mechanical wood pulp, where whitening is not necessary, resulting in lower environmental impact. Commonly, wood is the raw material for this final product, although it can be potentially substituted by lignocellulosic secondary residues such as sugarcane bagasse, since is an industrial residue stream that can replace primary dedicated biomass source of wood in. This value chain is detailed in Table 14.

Table 14. Value chain of napkins associated to the PRODCOM code.

PULP AND PAPER SECTOR		
Stage	PRODCOM	Sanitary paper
Final product	17.22.12.30	Napkins
Intermediate 2	17.12.20.30	Cellulose wadding for household or sanitary purposes, in rolls of a width > 36 cm or in rectangular (including square sheets) with at least one side > 36 cm in an unfolded state
Intermediate 1	17.11.14.00	Mechanical wood pulp; semi-chemical wood pulp; pulps of fibrous cellulosic material other than wood
Biological resource	-	Bagasse sugar cane fibre (primary residue)

Value chain

- Paper for graphic purpose [20]

As graphic paper, the paper for graphic purpose is the most produced and sold product in Europe. The production of paper from wood as raw material involves various steps depending on the type of paper. However, in order to increase the sustainability in paper production, recycled paper is the most common raw material. Considered a tertiary residue or waste, its conversion into the final graphic paper includes just one intermediate stage, which is the mechanical wood pulp based on PRODCOM database. This value chain is detailed in Table 15.

Table 15. Value chain of graphic paper associated to the PRODCOM code.

PULP AND PAPER SECTOR		
Stage	PRODCOM	Graphic paper
Final product	17.23.14.00	Paper for graphic purpose
Intermediate 1	17.11.14.00	Mechanical pulp; semi-chemical wood pulp; pulps of fibrous cellulosic material non wood
Biological resource	-	Recyclable paper (tertiary residue and wastes)

Value chain

- **Packaging paper (cartons, boxes and cases of paperboard) [20]**

As packaging paper, carton boxes and cases are the most widespread products, these products are made by corrugated paper or paperboard in sheets, and its properties can be improved by coating with microfibrillated cellulose (MFC). These cellulose microfibrils are spatially organized by parallel fibres linked by hydrogen bonds and other strong intermolecular chemical bonds, which give them great physical resistance. Due to its novelty, MFCs doesn't appear in the PRODCOM database, but they can be obtained through mechanical wood pulping, normally from coniferous or other softwoods, which are primary dedicated biological resources. This value chain is detailed in the Table 16.

Table 16. Value chain of cartons, boxes and cases associated to it PRODCOM code.

PULP AND PAPER SECTOR		
Stage	PRODCOM	Packaging paper
Final product	17.21.13.00	Cartons, boxes, and cases of corrugated paper
Intermediate 2	17.12.11.00	Corrugated paper and paperboard in rolls or sheets + coated (or not) with Microfibrillated Cellulose (MFC)
Intermediate 1	17.11.14.00	Mechanical pulp; semi-chemical wood pulp; pulps of fibrous cellulosic material non wood
Biological resource	-	Coniferous (primary dedicated)

3.2 Construction sector

Based on the methodology outlined in section 2.1, for the construction sector three value chains were selected, one per main subsectors identified. These main subsectors in the construction sector were identified through the report European Construction Sector Observatory (ECSSO) [2] which are illustrated in the following Figure 4:

Figure 4. Subsectors identified in construction sector.

The following final products from the Construction sector were selected based on the methodology described in section 2.1. and are further described below: Carpentry of wood for windows, Prefabricated buildings and Doors, frames and thresholds subflooring of wood.

- **Interior (carpentry of wood for windows) [21], [22]**

As interior building, wood frames for windows are the most produced and sold product in Europe. Windows frames are made by particle board by pressing wood debris, such as sawdust and dust, with resins and glue, typically followed by painting and varnishing steps. These products are moisture and mechanically resistant, and normally the feedstock is coniferous wood. This value chain is detailed in Table 17. Table 17

Table 17. Value chain of windows frames associated to the PRODCOM code.

CONSTRUCTION SECTOR		
Stage	PRODCOM	Interior construction
Final product	16.23.11.00	Carpentry of wood: windows frames
Intermediate 2	16.21.12.00	Particle board of wood
Intermediate 1	16.10.21.10	Coniferous wood continuously shaped (including strips and friezes for parquet flooring, not assembled)
Biological resource	-	Coniferous (primary dedicated)

Value chain

- **Building envelop (prefabricated buildings and insulation) [22], [23]**

As building envelop, prefabricated buildings and insulations are the most produced and sold construction product in Europe. Based on specific literature, conventional insulations can be substituted with biobased alternatives, such as straw insulations, using a primary residue of straw as a biological resource. For its manufacturing, the particles of straw should be organised into oriented strand board (OSB) for resistance and durability. This value chain is detailed in Table 18.

Table 18. Value chain of straw insulations associated to the PRODCOM code.

CONSTRUCTION SECTOR		
Stage	PRODCOM	Building envelop
Final product	16.23.20.00	Prefabricated buildings and insulations
Intermediate 2	16.21.13.16	Oriented Strand Board
Intermediate 1	16.10.25.05	Non wood in chips or particles
Biological resource	-	Wheat Straw (primary residue)

Value chain

- **Wooden structures (doors, frames and thresholds subflooring of wood) [24]**

Doors, frames, and subflooring correspond to a major share of the European production in the construction sector. It is reported in literature that conventional doors and floors can be made by hemp, which although being a primary dedicated biological resource, has a short rotation than conventional wood. These particles of hemp can be organized into fibreboard with high resistance to obtain doors or floors. This value chain is detailed in Table 19.

Table 19. Value chain of doors, frames and floors associated to the PRODCOM code.

CONSTRUCTION SECTOR		
Stage	PRODCOM	Wooden structures
Final product	16.23.11.50	Doors, frames and thresholds subflooring of wood
Intermediate 2	16.21.15.43	Fibreboard (excluding medium density fibreboard MDF) of wood or other ligneous materials, whether or not bonded with resins or other organic substances of a density exceeding 0,8 g/cm ³
Intermediate 1	16.10.25.05	Non wood in chips or particles
Biological resource	-	Hemp (primary dedicated)

3.3 Chemistry sector

Based on the methodology outlined in section 2.1, for the chemistry sector three value chains were selected, one per main subsectors identified. These main subsectors in the chemistry sector were identified through the report Roadmap for the chemical industry in Europe towards a Bioeconomy [8], which are in the following Figure 5:

Figure 5. Subsectors identified in chemistry sector.

According to the amount of production and sales of different products with potential to be biobased, collected in PRODCOM, one final product from each sub sector with a high impact on the market is selected: lubricants, solvents and adhesives, whose value chains are detailed below.

- **Lubricants [25]**

As lubricants, the biobased final products selected are the preparations without petroleum oil or bituminous minerals, excluding the ones used for treatment of textiles, leather, hides and other materials. According to the literature, most of lubricants are based on mineral oil, but the industry is trying to formulate biodegradable lubricants from vegetable oils, especially palm oil, due to its amphiphilic nature consisting of long fatty acid chains and polar groups. Accordingly, this chemical structure helps in the strong interactions required by lubricants.

The main chemical compound of potentially 100% biobased lubricants is polyoxy-ethylene olete, an emulsifying agent derived from oleic acid, which can be found in vegetable oils such as palm oil. While this oil is a primary dedicated biological resource, used oils are a much more sustainable alternative (tertiary residues). This value chain is described in the Table 20.

Table 20. Value chain of lubricants associated to the PRODCOM code.

CHEMICAL SECTOR		
Stage	PRODCOM	Lubricants
Final product	20.59.41.79	Lubricating preparations not containing petroleum oil or bituminous mineral oils, excluding the ones used for treatment of textiles, leather, hides, foreskins, or other materials
Intermediate 2	-	Polyoxy-ethylene olete
Intermediate 1	20.14.31.30	Industrial oleic acid
Biological resource	10.41.25.10	Vegetable oils (primary dedicated or tertiary residue)

Value chain

- Solvents [26]

As solvents, solvents for cleaning are the most produced and sold product in Europe, using as reference butane-1,4-diol or tetramethylene glycol which can reach a biobased carbon content of 100%. Sugars from maize can be converted by fermentation into a range of organic acids, among those succinic acid, the precursor of butane-1,4-diol through a hydrogenation reaction. This value chain is described in the Table 21.

Table 21. Value chain of solvents associated to the PRODCOM code.

CHEMICAL SECTOR		
Stage	PRODCOM	Solvents
Final product	-	Solvent for cleaning
Intermediate 2	20.14.23.38	Butane-1,4-diol or tetramethylene glycol (1,4-butanediol) having a biogenic carbon content of 100 % by mass
Intermediate 1	-	Succinic acid
Biological resource	-	Maize crop (primary dedicated)

Value chain

- **Adhesives [27]**

Traditionally, adhesives formulations are largely fossil-based, although natural resins can substitute them and thus increase the biobased content of the final product. This new type of adhesive uses tall oil obtained as a by-product from the wood pulping in kraft mills from pine trees that can be used for incorporation into sustainable, natural resins and glues. This value chain is described in the Table 22.

Table 22. Value chain of adhesives associated to the PRODCOM code.

CHEMICAL SECTOR		
Stage	PRODCOM	Adhesives
Final product	20.52.10.10	Adhesives based on natural polymers
Intermediate 1	20.14.71.30	Tall oil resins
Biological resource	-	Tall oil (secondary residue)

Value chain

3.4 Plastic sector

Based on the methodology outlined in section 2.1, for the plastic sector three value chains were selected, one per main subsectors identified. These main subsectors in the plastic sector were identified through the European Bioplastic Market report [9], which are illustrated in the following Figure 6:

Figure 6. Subsectors identified in plastic sector.

According to the amount of production and sales of different products with potential to be biobased, collected in PRODCOM, one final product from each sub sector with a high impact on the market is selected: Tableware and kitchenware, Mulch film and Sacks and bags of polymers of ethylene, whose value chains are detailed below.

- **Consumer goods (tableware and kitchenware of plastic) [28]**

As consumer goods, kitchenware is the most produced and sold product in Europe. The main part of these products is made by fossil-based plastics, although the increasing environmental awareness is largely promoting the development of biobased alternatives such as polylactic acid (PLA). This bioplastic comes from the polymerization of lactic acid, which is produced by bacteria from genre *Lactobacillus* in the fermentation of sugars, such as maize starch, being a primary dedicated biological resource. This value chain is described in the Table 23.

Table 23. Value chain of tableware and kitchenware associated to the PRODCOM code.

PLASTIC SECTOR		
Stage	PRODCOM	Consumer goods
Final product	22.29.23.20	Tableware and kitchenware of plastic
Intermediate 2	20.16.40.90	PLA
Intermediate 1	-	Lactic acid
Biological resource	-	Maize (primary dedicated)

Value chain

- **Agriculture (mulch film) [29]**

In the agriculture area, mulch films are the most produced and sold product in Europe. Based on specific literature, conventional agricultural (mulch) film is made by fossil based plastic (LDPE), which is not biodegradable and can cause littering in the environment, but it can be substituted with biobased alternatives, such as biodegradable bioplastic polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA). PHA is an organic acid produced by *Pseudomonas* or *Bacillus* genres. For the initial cultivation of this bacteria any organic waste can be used, especially food waste due to its high carbon content. This value chain is described in the Table 24.

Table 24. Value chain of mulch film associated to the PRODCOM code.

PLASTIC SECTOR		
Stage	PRODCOM	Agriculture
Final product	-	Mulch film

Intermediate 2	20.16.40.90	PHA
Intermediate 1	-	Organic acids
Biological resource	-	Organic waste (tertiary residue and waste)

Value chain

- **Packaging (sacks and bags of polymers of ethylene) [30]**

Packaging, sacs and bags are the most produced and sold product in Europe. Based on specific literature, the main part of these products is made of conventional (fossil-based) polyethylene. However, it is possible to produce ethylene from biobased sources via bioethylene production, which involves the fermentation of sugars, which are firstly converted into ethanol and further dehydrated to obtain ethylene. In this value chain, the feedstock comes mainly from sugarcane or sugar beet due to their high sugar content and is described in the Table 25.

Table 25. Value sacs and bags of polymers of ethylene associated to the PRODCOM code.

PLASTIC SECTOR		
Stage	PRODCOM	Packaging
Final product	22.22.11.00	Sacks and bags of polymers of ethylene (including cones)
Intermediate 2	20.16.10.39	Polyethylene having a specific gravity < 0,94, in primary forms (excluding linear)
Intermediate 1	20.14.11.30	Ethylene
Biological resource	10.81.11.00	Raw cane and beet sugar in solid form, not containing added flavouring or colouring matter (primary dedicated)

Value chain

3.5 Textile sector

Based on the methodology outlined in section 2.1, for the textile sector three value chains were selected, one per main subsectors identified. These main subsectors in the textile sector were identified through the European report of Advanced technologies for textile industry [10], which are illustrated in the following Figure 7:

Figure 7. Subsectors identified in textile sector.

According to the amount of production and sales of different products with potential to be biobased, collected in PRODCOM, one final product from each sub sector with a high impact on the market was selected: t-shirts, singlets and vests, table linen of flax and conveyor belts.

- **Clothing (T-shirts, singlets, and vests) [31]**

As abovementioned, T-shirts, singlets and vest are the most sold product in Europe. The textile sector is one of the most energy-intensive and resource-intensive due to its necessity of fossil-based chemicals to produce synthetic fibres such as nylon. To create a more sustainable sector, biobased textiles are preferred, and natural fibers such as cotton cover a large part of the market. For instance, despite being a primary dedicated biological resource, cotton can replace non-renewable resources in the production of the yarn and fabrics (compared to synthetic fibers). This value chain is described in the Table 26.

Table 26. value chain of t-shirts, singlets and vests associated to the PRODCOM code

TEXTILE SECTOR		
Stage	PRODCOM	Clothing
Final product	14.14.30.00	T-shirts, singlets and vests, knitted or crocheted
Intermediate 2	13.91.11	Pile fabrics, terry fabrics knitted or crocheted
Intermediate 1	13.10.61.53	Yarn of combed cotton, n.p.r.s., for knitted fabrics and hosiery
Biological resource	13.10.25.00	Cotton, carded or combed (primary dedicated)

Value chain

- **Furniture (table linen of flax) [32], [33]**

Furniture textile is usually produced using fossil-based synthetic fibre based yarns. However, a biobased alternative is using linen of flax, with a flax content by weight higher than 85%. This value chain is described in the Table 27.

Table 27. value chain of table linen of flax associated to the PRODCOM code.

TEXTILE SECTOR		
Stage	PRODCOM	Furniture
Final product	13.92.13.55	Table linen of flax
Intermediate 2	13.20.13.30	Woven fabrics of flax, containing \geq 85 % by weight of flax
Intermediate 1	13.10.71.10	Flax yarn
Biological resource	13.10.29.00	Other vegetable textile fibres, processed but not spun (primary dedicated)

Value chain			

- **Industry (conveyor belts) [34]**

In the industry, conveyor belts are used to transport materials. Specifically, bakery and food industries use conveyor belts produced from biological resources, such as wool joined with other non-biological materials. First, the wool is carded to remove impurities and get the yarns, which are twisted together to form a strong and durable yarn. This intermediate is knitted to obtain the woven fabrics which can be used to prepare conveyor belts and are joined with other materials, like acrylic fibres, to enhance its mechanical properties. This value chain is described in the Table 28.

Table 28. value chain of conveyor belts associated to the PRODCOM code

TEXTILE SECTOR		
Stage	PRODCOM	Industry
Final product	13.96.16.50	Textile wicks, conveyor belts or belting (including reinforced with metal or other material)
Intermediate 2	13.20.12.60	Woven fabrics of combed wool or combed fine animal hair; woven fabrics of coarse animal hair
Intermediate 1	13.10.50.10	Yarn of combed wool or fine animal hair, n.p.r.s.

Biological resource	10.11.41.00	Greasy wool not carded or combed (including fleecewashed wool) (primary dedicated)
Value chain		

3.6 Woodworking sector

Based on the methodology outlined in section 2.1, for the woodworking sector three value chains were selected, one per main subsectors identified. These main subsectors in the woodworking sector were identified through the Forest based sector platform [11], which are illustrated in the following Figure 8:

Figure 8. Subsectors identified in woodworking sector.

According to the amount of production and sales of different products with potential to be biobased, collected in PRODCOM, one final product from each sub sector with a high impact on the market was selected: Cases and boxes of wood, Wooden frames for painting or mirrors and Wooden bedroom furniture.

- **Carpentry pieces (Cases and boxes and similar packaging of wood) [33], [35]**

Carpentry pieces, cases, boxes, and similar packaging of are the most sold product in Europe. The main part of these products is biobased, as its raw material is wood. However, in this case, the challenge is to substitute the primary dedicated feedstock or at least to combine it with residues such as sawdust (secondary residue). The wood is compacted into laminated panels, which can be then stacked into boxes. This value chain is described in the Table 29.

Table 29. Value chain of packaging of wood associated to the PRODCOM code.

WOODWORKING SECTOR		
Stage	PRODCOM	Carpentry pieces
Final product	16.24.13.20	Cases, boxes, crates, drums and similar packings of wood
Intermediate 1	16.21.16.00	Other plywood, veneered panels, and similar laminated wood
Biological resource	-	Residues from sawn wood (secondary residues)

Value chain

- **Manufacture articles (Wooden frames for paintings, photographs, mirrors or similar objects) [33], [36]**

As manufacture articles, wooden frames for mirror or photographs are the most sold in Europe. The biobased industry is trying to substitute virgin wood with more sustainable alternatives such as wheat straw, which can be structured and incorporated into wood boards with suitable properties. This value chain is described in the Table 30.

Table 30. Value chain of wooden frames associated to the PRODCOM code.

WOODWORKING SECTOR		
Stage	PRODCOM	Manufacture articles
Final product	16.29.14.20	Wooden frames for paintings, photographs, mirrors or similar objects
Intermediate 1	16.21.14.50	Particle board and similar board of ligneous materials
Biological resource	-	Ligneous materials (wheat straw) (primary residues) + wood (primary dedicated)

Value chain

- **Furniture (Wooden bedroom furniture) [33], [37]**

As furniture, bedroom furniture is the most sold in Europe. Traditionally it was made by virgin wood, but new alternatives have emerged to substitute it with secondary wood residues such as sawdust of pine. When combined with resins and other lignocelluloses, these materials can reach the required density to obtain MDF boards, which are suitable for home furniture due to its properties. This value chain is described in the Table 31.

Table 31. value chain of wooden bedroom furniture associated to the PRODCOM code.

WOODWORKING SECTOR		
Stage	PRODCOM	Furniture
Final product	31.09.12.30	Wooden bedroom furniture (excluding builders' fittings for cupboards to be built into walls, mattress supports, lamps and lighting fittings, floor standing mirrors, seats)
Intermediate 2	16.21.15.29	Medium density fibreboard (MDF), of wood or other ligneous materials, whether or not bonded with resins or other organic substances, of a thickness exceeding 9 mm
Intermediate 1	16.10.11.36	Pine wood (<i>Pinus sylvestris</i> L.) sawn or chipped lengthwise, sliced or peeled, of a thickness > 6 mm
Biological resource	-	Residues from sawn wood (-) (secondary residues)

Value chain

The diagram illustrates the value chain for wooden bedroom furniture. It starts with a window icon on the left, followed by a green arrow pointing to a wood chip icon. A second green arrow points to another wood chip icon, and a final green arrow points to a bed icon on the right.

4. Ranking of the value chains

4.1 Criteria and subcriteria ranking value

According to the methodology described in the section 2.2.1, different experts were engaged in order to assess the weight of each criteria and subcriteria defined (section 2.2.2). As a result, 9 experts (members of the Advisory Board and experts from the sister projects) provided feedback.

These experts first scored which criteria they considered more important than others and how much more important. For example, the “technical criteria” is more important than the “environmental criteria” and the intensity of the importance is 5 (“Experience and judgement strongly favor one element over another”) according to the Saaty’s scale. With these data and applying the AHP methodology, the following weights were obtained for each of the 3 criteria (on a scale of 0 to 100). The weight obtained in each criteria are indicated in Table 32 and it can be seen how experts have considered that practically all three criteria analysed are of similar importance when talking about bio-based value chains.

Table 32. Weight of each criteria according the feedback provided by 9 expert.

Criteria	Final weight of each criteria and subcriteria
Environmental	32.12
Socioeconomic	34.72
Technical	33.16

Secondly, the same methodology was done for the case of the subcriteria, the experts indicate which subcriteria that belong to the same criteria are more important than the others and how much according to the Saaty’s scale, and as result applying the AHP mathematical model the weight of each subcriteria was obtained, Table 33.

Table 33. Weight of each subcriteria according the feedback provided by 9 experts.

Subcriteria	Final weight of each subcriteria
Environmental	
Potential biobased share of the final product	6.73
Estimated percentage share of biobased products in total marketed	8.22
Presence of environmental concerns of the conventional chain	10.51
Relevance to EU policy priorities	6.65
Socioeconomic	
Market size	7.56

Subcriteria	Final weight of each subcriteria
Market growth	11.98
Presence of social concerns	15.18
Technical	
Innovative character of the value chain	8.41
Feedstock availability in the EU	5.95
Biobased final product produced in the EU	4.62
Valorisation of residues and wastes	14.18

Based on the weights obtained to each subcriteria (Table 33), the three subcriteria that will have the greatest impact on the final ranking will be:

- Presence of social concerns (15.18)
- Valorisation of residues and wastes (14.18)
- Market growth (11.98)

On the other hand, the three that will have the least impact will be:

- Relevance to EU policy priorities (6.65)
- Feedstock availability in the EU (5.95)
- Biobased final product produced in the EU (4.62).

These final weight of each criteria and subcriteria together with the output from section 4.2 will be considered in order to rank the biobased value chain selected (section 4.3).

4.2 Score of each subcriteria in each value chain

4.2.1 Pulp and paper sector

According to the results, reflected in Table 34, obtained from each of the 3 value chains, it can be concluded that the sector Pulp and paper is characterised by a high level of biobased share (CE-1). This is a predictable result given that paper is itself a biobased product, which in turn implies that there is little potential to substitute fossil-based products (CE-2) with it.

As for the other environmental sub-criteria, the pulp and paper sector is at an intermediate level in terms of environmental concern (mentioned in section 2.2.2), however the scores are quite different as the raw materials used are from different biological categories (tertiary residue for graphical, primary residue for sanitary and primary dedicated for packaging) (CE-3), while the three chains are found relevant but only slightly supported by EU policy priorities (CE-4).

On the socioeconomic side, for market size the packaging is found to be prominent in the Pulp and paper sector (CS-1), while for market growth (CS-2) all three value chains score in general terms as medium-low.

Given the long history of this material, its innovative character (CT-1) is only high in those cases where the product does not consist exclusively of paper or where a less conventional raw material is used, which is the case of graphical paper from recycled paper and sanitary paper produced with secondary lignocellulosic residues.

The EU production capacity for covering its internal market demand for the products addressed in this sector (CT-3) is high, given that the pulp & paper industry is very strong, particularly in the northern EU.

Table 34 Score of each subcriteria in the value chain of the Pulp and paper sector

Product		CE-1	CE-2	CE-3	CE-4	CS-1	CS-2	CS-3	CT-1	CT-2	CT-3	CT-4
Graphical Paper	Value	9	1	8	7	4	3	8	6	9	8	9
	Reference	[38]	-		[39]	[40]	[40]	[16], [41]	[42]	[5]	[5]	-
Sanitary Paper	Value	7	2	6	6	2	5	6	6	1	8	6
	Reference	[43]	[44]		[39]	[40]	[40]	[15], [16]	[45]	[15]	[33]	-
Packaging	Value	9	1	2	5	8	4	8	1	8	8	4
	Reference	[46]	-		[39]	[47]	[47]	[15], [16]	[46]	[15]	[33]	-

As far as the criteria related to the main raw material of the products are concerned, for social concerns (CS-3), no major problem is seen for the sector, taking into account the quantities produced within the EU and those imported, as well as the main exporting countries of such material. However, as far as the availability of feedstock in the EU is concerned, and as can be seen in Figure 9, Figure 10 and Figure 11, consumption can be entirely or mostly from the EU's own production or 100% from outside the EU (CT-2), using everything from dedicated raw materials to tertiary and secondary waste (CT-4).

Figure 9 Percentage of Paper for graphical purposes imports of raw materials and social level of its main exporters

Figure 10 Percentage of Napkins imports of raw materials and social level of its main exporters

Figure 11 Percentage of Cartons, boxes and cases of corrugated paper imports of raw materials and social level of its main exporters

4.2.2 Construction sector

As with the Pulp and paper sector and as indicated in Table 35, the construction sector has products with a high level of biobased share (CE-1). However, in contrast to the Pulp and paper sector, the replacement potential within this sector for fossil-based or other energy intensive construction material such as concrete and steel (CE-2) is much higher.

In general terms, the construction sector scores low-moderately in terms of the presence of environmental concerns (CE-3) since the construction sector is at an intermediate level in terms of environmental concern (mentioned in section 2.2.2), and the raw materials used are from different primary dedicated and primary residues biological categories (primary residue for building envelop and primary dedicated for interior construction and wooden structures). The same is true for the relevance with regard to EU policy priorities (CE-4), except for the interior construction value chain where use of wood in construction and long term carbon storage is at the focus point of recent EU policy priorities. While for the feedstock of the other two value chains that are straw and hemp, no direct support by EU policy yet seen.

Despite this relevance of wood based interior construction in the political sphere, its market (CS-1) does not exceed 10 billion USD, far below the 100-150 billion USD the other two products studied in this sector. While for market growth (CS-2) all three value chains score in general terms as medium to medium-high, with the interior construction showing lowest CAGR of the three cases, between 4% and 5%.

The latter results may be partly justified by the current lack of innovation (CT-1) of the interior construction product compared to the other two products where a less conventional raw material is used instead of wood.

The EU production capacity for covering its internal market demand for the products addressed in this sector (CT-3) is high, given that the value chains are largely wood-based, and EU has a well-established forestry industry particularly in the northern EU.

Table 35 Score of each subcriteria in the value chain of the Construction sector

Product		CE-1	CE-2	CE-3	CE-4	CS-1	CS-2	CS-3	CT-1	CT-2	CT-3	CT-4
Interior Construction	Value	8	5	3	9	1	5	8	2	8	8	4
	Reference	[48]	[49]	[50]	[39]	[47]	[47]	[15], [16]	[21]	[15]	[33]	-
Building Envelope	Value	9	9	6	6	4	7	8	5	9	8	6
	Reference	[46]	[51]	[50]	[39]	[41]	[41]	[15], [16]	[46]	[15]	[33]	-
Wooden structures	Value	8	5	3	5	4	6	8	7	9	8	1
	Reference	[46]	[49]	[50]	[39]	[41]	[41]	[15], [16]	[52]	[15]	[33]	-

As these are products whose raw materials are produced in large quantities or entirely in the EU (CT-2) and the EU scores are very well on the social index, as reflected in Figure 12, Figure 13 and Figure 14, these products are attributed a low social concern (CS-3).. In this case, of the three chains studied, only one of them (Building envelope) valorises residues (CT-4), these being primary residues (wheat straw) for high value application.

Figure 12 Percentage of Builder's joinery and carpentry of wood for windows imports of raw materials and social level of its main exporters

Figure 13 Percentage of Insulations imports of raw materials and social level of its main exporters

Figure 14 Percentage of Door, frames and thresholds subflooring of wood imports of raw materials and social level of its main exporters

4.2.3 Chemistry sector

The products studied within the chemistry sector also have a high biobased share (CE-1), as well as a great potential to replace fossil-based products (CE-2) by providing direct functional replacement of the fossil-based counterparts.

The chemical industry is widely regarded as one of the most polluting sectors due to the pollutants it emits, its chemical discharges, the effects its leaks can have and the fact that the hazardous waste generated by this industry can contaminate air, water and soil, resulting in a significant risk to human health and the environment. This is clearly reflected in two of its products being rated as having the worst score in this aspect when the raw material used is primary dedicated (lubricants and solvents), however for the adhesive value chain since the raw material used belong to a secondary residues category the score is higher (CE-3). With regard to adhesives, which would generate a more moderate concern, this rating is assigned to them, bearing in mind that the raw material used is a secondary waste, while the other products use "Primary dedicated resources. Regarding EU policy perspective (CE-4) three chains are found relevant, with only adhesives being slightly supported that use lignocellulosic resource whereas food crops are utilized in production of lubricants (vegetable oils) and solvents (maize).

The size of the market (CS-1) in these cases are relatively low in comparison to the scale of the products described above for the two sectors. In relation to market growth (CS-2), apart from solvents, which shows good growth, the rest of the products score moderately.

As far as the innovative character of these value chains (CT-1) is concerned, the products show high score with biobased chemicals involving novel conversion technologies.

The EU production capacity for covering its internal market demand for the products addressed in this sector (CT-3) is relatively high, given that most of the current production of biobased lubricants, solvents and adhesives is covered internally. Nonetheless, it is important to mention that the absolute production/consumption of biobased chemicals is still very low, not only in EU but worldwide, as most of the marketed products in this sector are fossil-based. This is the result of a combination of feedstock and supply chain limitations, competition with food value chains, and technological immaturity in the case of novel production processes resulting in difficulty in cost competitive production with respect to fossil-based counterparts. Therefore, the CT-3 results here described show that the (currently small) market for biobased chemicals is covered internally in Europe, but there is an ever-growing demand and need to move to sustainable value chains using biological resources.

Table 36 Score of each subcriteria in the value chain of the Chemistry sector

Product		CE-1	CE-2	CE-3	CE-4	CS-1	CS-2	CS-3	CT-1	CT-2	CT-3	CT-4
Lubricants	Value	7	9	1	5	4	4	7	5	1	8	4
	Reference	[53]	[54]	[8]	[39]	[47]	[47]	[15], [16]	[25]	[15]	[8]	-
Solvents	Value	9	9	1	5	2	7	8	7	7	7	1
	Reference	[46]	[8]	[8]	[39]	[47]	[47]	[15], [16]	[55]	[15]	[8]	-
Adhesives	Value	8	7	8	7	3	5	8	8	9	8	8
	Reference	[56]	[40]	[8]	[39]	[47]	[47]	[15], [16]	[57]	[15]	[26]	-

As can be seen in Figure 15, Figure 16 and Figure 17, the chemical sector sees all or a large proportion of its demand for raw materials met by the EU itself (CT-2), which means that these products are of low social concern given the EU's high value in the social index (CS-3) The only one that does not meet these conditions are the lubricants, whose raw material would be imported in its entirety, from a number of countries with a lower value than the EU in the social index and therefore generating greater social concern than the rest of the chemical products as a consequence of the fact that the social level of the main exporters of palm oil is lower than that of the EU.

Regarding CT-4, both lubricants as a raw material that can be considered as primary dedicated or tertiary residue (according to the source) for this reason have an intermediate score, solvents rely on the use primary dedicated resources and adhesives to a secondary residue.

Figure 15 Percentage of Lubricants imports of raw materials and social level of its main exporters

Figure 16 Percentage of Solvent for cleaning imports of raw materials and social level of its main exporters

Figure 17 Percentage of Adhesives imports of raw materials and social level of its main exporters

4.2.4 Plastic sector

The products studied in this study for the plastics sector are characterised, as can be seen in Table 37, by high biobased shares (CE-1), as well as a great potential to replace fossil-based plastics (CE-2) by providing direct functional replacement of the fossil-based counterparts.

The plastics sector is considered the second most polluting sector after the chemical industry, as a result of its emissions, its production from fossil fuels and the fact that millions of plastic waste products reach the oceans and damage marine life. With this in mind, the main reason why this mulch film (used in agriculture and biodegradable) has such a low concern compared to the other two products is that by using a tertiary waste and not a resource primarily dedicated to the manufacture of the product, it would not compete with food production as is the case with the other (CE-3).

For plastics in agriculture, there is clear EU policy interest (CE-4) concerning the Framework for biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics, and the future review foreseen for the Fertiliser Directive (2019) with a view on requiring mulch films to be biodegradable.

In the other two product cases, the same level of EU support has yet not been seen as a result of the use of dedicated biological raw materials used primarily for these products rather than the use of residues (CT-4), where it is important to ensure sustainable sourcing and favourable environmental performance compared to the fossil-based counterparts. Yet, the existing support for the production of plastics from biobased feedstocks result in a score showing slight support.

On the socioeconomic side (CS-1 and CS-2), the market is dominated mainly by consumer goods, which show a relatively low growth rate. While for the other two products the situation is the opposite i.e. the market size is quite low, but growth is significant.

As regards to the innovativeness of the value chains (CT-1), all show good scores, especially in the case of consumer goods and agriculture, as these are either new entrants to the market or very poorly marketed products. However, the only one that is using tertiary residue and waste type of feedstock is the mulch film product of agriculture (organic waste to PHA), while the two other products use primarily dedicated resources for the production of the product (CT-4).

The EU production capacity for covering its internal market demand for the products addressed in this sector (CT-3) is relatively high, given that most of the production of consumer, agricultural and packaging plastic goods is covered internally. Similar to the chemical sector, it is important to mention that the absolute production/consumption of biobased plastics is still very low, not only in EU but worldwide, as most of the marketed products in this sector are fossil-based. This is the result of a combination of feedstock and supply chain limitations, competition with food value chains, and technological immaturity in the case of novel production processes resulting in difficulty in cost competitive production with respect to fossil-based counterparts. Therefore, the CT-3 results here described show that the (currently small) biobased plastics market is mostly covered internally in Europe, but there is an ever-growing demand and need to move to sustainable value chains using biological resources. For instance, the actual bioplastics and PLA production in EU were of 588k tonnes and 120k tonnes respectively (2019 basis) [9], being far lower than the demand for plastic consumer and packaging goods, which are in the order of millions of tonnes – in the same year, 15.4 millions of tonnes of plastic packaging waste were produced just in EU [58]. Only the mulch film production of ca. 80k tonnes per year (targeted by the agricultural sector) can be fully covered by the EU bioplastics production, as this is relatively small niche. Nonetheless, the PHA production is even more niche (ca. 23k tonnes produced per year). Biobased PE production in EU is still low (87k tonnes produced per year) [9], yet it provides a direct drop-in substitute for the fossil-based PE that has many applications including bags.

Table 37 Score of each subcriteria in the value chain of the Plastic sector

Product		CE-1	CE-2	CE-3	CE-4	CS-1	CS-2	CS-3	CT-1	CT-2	CT-3	CT-4
Consumer goods	Value	9	9	2	6	9	3	8	8	7	7	1
	Reference	[59]	[60]	[61]	[39]	[41]	[41]	[15], [16]	[62]	[15]	[9]	-
Agriculture	Value	9	9	8	9	1	8	8	9	9	9	9
	Reference	[63]	[64]	[61]	[39]	[65]	[65]	[15], [16], [66]	[67], [68]	[15], [33]	[33]	-
Packaging	Value	8	9	2	6	2	9	8	6	9	8	1
	Reference	[46]	[69]	[61]	[39]	[69]	[69]	[15], [16]	[46]	[15]	[70]	-

In this case, the current demand for the raw materials needed for these value chains is largely covered by EU production (CT-2), resulting in low social concerns (CS-3).

Figure 18 Percentage of Tableware and kitchenware of PLA imports of raw materials and social level of its main exporters

Figure 19 Percentage of Mulch film of PHA imports of raw materials and social level of its main exporters

Figure 20 Percentage of Sacks and bags of polymers of ethylene imports of raw materials and social level of its main exporters

4.2.5 Textile sector

The value chains selected for the textile sector encompasses 100% biobased products (CE-1), which, with the exception of clothing product, have significant potential to replace fossil-based products (CE-2). This stems from the consideration that the higher the presence of bio-based products on the market, the less potential there is for this product to replace a large amount of fossil-based products. This is the case in the textile sector where, in addition to the fact that cotton (selected raw material) is quite widespread, there are other bio-based materials competing with it (jute, wool raw silk, ...).

The textile sector is at a low level in terms of environmental concern (mentioned in section 2.2.2), however the scores are intermediate and equal in all the cases since the raw materials used are from the same biological categories (primary dedicated) (CE-3) within the sector are mostly coming from the clothing product associated with the cultivation of cotton (which is considered to have higher impact than flax and wool used in the other two products). Clothing product is seen to have a high priority in the EU environmental policy framework (CE-4), because of the existence of the sustainable textiles strategy and existing support for biobased textiles.

According to the data collected, the market size (CS-1) of the products of the textile sector analysed is the lowest among all the sectors studied (pulp and paper, woodworking, construction, chemical and plastic), where at least one of the products has a high market size or the three products that make up the sector is not as low as in the present case.

As for market growth (CS-2), it is characterised by an average growth, not among the highest, but not as distant as in the case of market size.

As production of yarn from these natural raw materials are already well established the innovative character (CT-1) of these products score low. What is more recently developed is the use of biobased plastics as alternatives to fossil-based synthetic fibres that would score higher for this category.

The EU production [71] capacity for covering its internal market demand for the products addressed in this sector (CT-3) is medium-low, especially in the case of clothing. For instance, imports (mainly by China, followed by India and Pakistan) cover a large share of the European clothing market, due to various factors, such as: *i*) a booming industry that largely promotes fast fashion resulting in overconsumption and disposal of clothes; *ii*) the ever-increasing outsourcing of production to lower-cost countries. It is expected that the pressing environmental and social concerns related to this industry will lessen the EU dependency on imports due to tighter regulations, the development of efficient recycling technologies and of novel value chains that use residual, local feedstocks to produce textiles, as well as changes in consumption habits.

Table 38 Score of each subcriteria in the value chain of the Textile sector

Product		CE-1	CE-2	CE-3	CE-4	CS-1	CS-2	CS-3	CT-1	CT-2	CT-3	CT-4
Clothing	Value	9	5	4	8	2	5	8	1	8	2	1
	Reference	[72], [73]	[74]	[75]	[39]	[76]	[76]	[15], [16]	[77]	[15]	[33]	-
Furniture	Value	9	7	4	5	1	5	8	1	9	6	4
	Reference	[32]	[78]	[75]	[39]	[79]	[79]	[15], [16]	[80]	[15]	[33]	-
Industry	Value	9	6	4	5	1	4	8	1	9	6	1

	Reference	[34]	[40]	[75]	[39]	[40]	[40]	[15], [16]	[81]	[15]	[33]	
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When analysing the sub-criteria related to raw materials it can be seen, as depicted in Figure 21, Figure 22 and Figure 23, that the EU has a good enough production to cover most of its demand (CT-2) for the relevant raw materials and that therefore, given the generally good level in the social field in the EU, the raw material also meets this level (CS-3).

Figure 21 Percentage of T-shirts of Cotton imports of raw materials and social level of its main exporters

Figure 22 Percentage of Table linen imports of raw materials and social level of its main exporters

Figure 23 Percentage of Conveyor belts of wool imports of raw materials and social level of its main exporters

4.2.6 Woodworking sector

For the woodworking sector, it was natural that, as in the case of the pulp and paper sector, the selected products are 100% biobased materials (CE-1). And as with the pulp and paper sector, the potential to replace fossil-based products is very low (CE-2) since wood is the conventional resource used in this sector.

Regarding the environmental concern (CE-3) this sector presents the low environmental impact (mentioned in section 2.2.2), for this reason in the case of using tertiary residues (carpentry pieces and furniture) the scores are the highest and intermediate for the case of manufacture articles value chain (since it is a mix of primary dedicated and primary residues). The furniture product case uses sawdust (secondary residue) as resource resulting in low environmental concern.

As far as relevance to EU policy priorities (CE-4) is concerned, while the three chains are found relevant only slightly supported by EU policy priorities.

The market size of the products in this sector (CS-1) is low, with the exception of the furniture product which is higher. The market growth (CS-2) for all three value chains score average.

Due to the established products and technologies in this sector, the score for the level of innovation (CT-1) is low.

The EU production capacity for covering its internal market demand for the products addressed in this sector (CT-3) is high, given that the value chains are largely wood-based and EU has a well-established forestry industry.

Table 39 Score of each subcriteria in the value chain of the Woodworking sector

Product		CE-1	CE-2	CE-3	CE-4	CS-1	CS-2	CS-3	CT-1	CT-2	CT-3	CT-4
Carpentry pieces	Value	9	1	9	5	2	6	8	1	9	8	8
	Reference	[35]	-		[39]	[82]	[82]	[15], [16]	[83]	[15]	[33]	-
Manufacture articles	Value	9	1	5	6	1	6	8	4	9	7	6
	Reference	[36]	-		[39]	[40]	[40]	[15], [16]	[84]	[15]	[33]	-
Furniture	Value	9	2	9	6	6	5	8	1	9	8	8
	Reference	[37]	[85]		[39]	[47]	[47]	[15], [16]	[86]	[15]	[33]	-

In terms of raw materials, as depicted in Figure 24, Figure 25 and Figure 26, it is largely, if not entirely, supplied by its own production (CT-2), which, as has been shown so far, implies high social standards (CS-3). In addition to the fact that the sector is capable of using primary and secondary waste as raw material (CT-4).

Figure 24 Percentage of Carpentry pieces imports of raw materials and social level of its main exporters

Figure 25 Percentage of Wood frames imports of raw materials and social level of its main exporters

Figure 26. Percentage of Wooden bedroom furniture imports of raw materials and social level of its main exporters

4.3 Final ranking of the value chains

Considering the weight of each criteria and subcriteria (section 4.1) and the score of each subcriteria in each biobased value chain (section 4.2), a final ranking (Table 40) has been calculated in order to identify the biobased value chain that has the most contribution to sustainable development in the EU according to the methodology (which represent the following situation: high potential of biobased share, it can replace the dependence of current fossil based value chains, have low environmental and social concerns, supported by policy, have high market size, have high market growth, highly innovative, feedstock and production can be supplied within EU (not dependent on import), it valorise residues) described in detail in chapter 2.

Table 40. Final ranking of the biobased value chains.

Biobased value chain	Subsector	Sector	Final score (from 0 to 100)
Mulch film from organic waste	Agriculture	Plastics	89.09
Prefabricated buildings from wood and wheat straw	Building envelope	Construction	76.75
Adhesives from tall oil	Adhesives	Chemical	76.55
Paper for graphical purpose from recycled paper	Graphical Paper	Pulp and paper	72.85

Biobased value chain	Subsector	Sector	Final score (from 0 to 100)
Wooden bedroom furniture from Residues from sawn wood	Furniture	Woodworking	72.29
Cases, boxes, crates, drums and similar packings from coniferous wood	Carpentry pieces	Woodworking	68.61
Sacks and bags of polymers of ethylene from raw cane and beet sugar	Packaging	Plastics	65.37
Tableware and kitchenware of plastic from maize	Consumer goods	Plastics	64.05
Wooden frames for paintings, photographs, mirrors or similar object from ligneous materials (wheat straw + wood)	Manufacture articles	Woodworking	62.98
Doors, frames and thresholds subflooring from hemp	Wooden structures	Construction	60.77
Solvent for cleaning from maize	Solvents	Chemical	60.65
Builder's joinery and Carpentry for window from coniferous wood	Interior Construction	Construction	59.26
Table linen of flax	Furniture	Textile	58.75
Napkins from Bagasse sugar cane fibre	Sanitary Paper	Pulp and paper	56.79
Cartons, boxes and cases of corrugated paper from coniferous wood	Packaging	Pulp and paper	55.85
Lubricants from vegetable oil	Lubricants	Chemical	54.56
T-shirts, singlets and vests, knitted or crocheted from Cotton, carded or combed	Clothing	Textile	52.54
Textile wicks, conveyor belts or belting from Greasy wool not carded or combed	Industry	Textile	51.78

Table 40 presents the final ranking of biobased value chains based on their scores in different sectors and subsectors. The top-ranked biobased value chains are: (1st) mulch film from organic waste with a final score of 89.09 (which belong to the plastic sector and agriculture subsector), (2nd)

prefabricated buildings from wood and wheat straw with a score of 76.75 (which belong to the construction sector and building envelop subsector), and (3rd) adhesives from tall oil with a score of 76.55 ((which belong to the chemical sector and adhesives subsector).

Furthermore, in general terms, the average score of the biobased chains studied is 64.42, with a maximum score of 89.09 (quite remarkable compared to average) and a minimum score of 51.78, showing that no chain has a score below 50.

If the 6 sectors are compared, it can be seen that the biobased value chain studied (which includes the specific raw material as well as the final product obtained) actually has more impact than the sector to which this value chain belongs. Only the textile sector, whose 3 chains have low scores (are in the top 6 worst rated value chains), could be said to show the least contribution to the sustainable development in the EU, because the three value chain studied in this sector are from primary dedicated raw materials, there is no innovation in the value chains, and the market size is low.

As a conclusion, the ranking indicates that 'mulch film from organic waste' is the most promising biobased value chain, and 'textile wicks, conveyor belts, or belting from greasy wool not carded or combed' is the least promising biobased value chain, among the ones considered in this study. However, it is important to note that the final ranking depends on the weight of each criteria and sub-criteria (section 4.1), which may vary depending on the goals and priorities of different stakeholders, and the desk research carried out to score the subcriteria in each value chain (section 4.2).

5. Conclusions

Overall, the study of biobased value chains has demonstrated the importance of sustainable and circular economic models in achieving long-term economic growth and environmental sustainability. By leveraging the potential of biobased industries, Europe can become a global leader in the transition to a more sustainable, low-carbon economy. However, this will require continued investment in research and development, policy support, and cross-sectoral collaboration to fully realize the potential of these industries.

The study was focused on 18 selected value chains within six industrial sectors, 11 subcriteria that belong to 3 criteria were considered in order to assess which biobased value chains are implemented at market on a general level, can contribute more to transition from fossil-based products and improve the overall sustainability that is being sought by the EU.

The work has been mainly carried out through desk research and the opinion gathered from certain experts. The main result is a final ranking of the biobased value chains studies which reflects the potential of each of them within its respective sector and subsector, based on the scores obtained in different criteria and sub-criteria. The ranking can help stakeholders, policymakers, and investors to identify promising biobased value chains and to make informed decisions regarding investments, policies, and research and development initiatives.

From the ranking of the 18 selected value chains, the highest scoring 3 are:

- Mulch film from organic waste, which belong to the plastic sector.
- Prefabricated buildings from wood and wheat straw, which belong to the construction sector.
- Adhesives from tall oil, which belong to the chemical sector.

Comparing the six sectors, it is evident that the biobased value chain under examination, which encompasses the specific raw material and final product, has a greater impact than the sector it belongs to. However, the textile sector stands out with its three chains ranking among the bottom six rated value chains. As such, it may be considered to show the least contribution to the sustainable development in the EU, because the three value chains studied in this sector are from primary dedicated raw materials and there is no innovation in the value chains. This also shows the need for transition in this sector to alternative biological resources with the development of novel value chains that also reduce EU dependency on imports and the need for development of efficient recycling technologies and shift from fast to slow fashion.

Finally, it should be noted that the information obtained in this task will be further developed in other activities within the project, as an example:

- Task 2.2 will develop the trade flows of each biobased value chain selected in this task.
- Task 4.2 will select 3 value chains of this to study to be explored in more detail in the rest of the task of the WP4 (task 4.3, 4.4 and 4.5).

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About SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is an EU funded (Horizon Europe) project aiming at defining and promoting the adoption of effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels for industrial biobased systems to support tracing the sustainability (environmental, social, economic) of biobased products along the value chains and trades within the EU and globally for responsible production and consumption. This objective is realised by the development of a monitoring system, mapping of the current situation in global trade flows of biological resources and biobased products, and feasibility assessment from the adoption of certification schemes and labels considering actual economic as well as internalized environmental and social costs and benefits. The results of the project are leveraged to provide recommendations to four key target groups: policy makers, sustainability system community, industrial biobased value chain actors, and regional bioeconomy stakeholders. These ambitions are addressed by a strong, well-balanced and multi-disciplinary consortium comprised of 5 complementary partners. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED thereby supports the development of harmonized system requirements, continuous improvement of sustainability certification schemes and labels and contributes towards establishing a circular, climate-neutral and sustainable biobased industry.

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